

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

2024

No 7

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

74-91 xalqaro daraja
ISSN: 2992-8982

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:
Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:
Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

*Elektron nashr. 348 sahifa.
E'lon qilishga 2024-yil 25-iyulda ruxsat etildi.*

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, t.f.d., prof., O'zR Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vaziri
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, i.f.d., O'zR Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vaziri o'rinbosari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, i.f.d., prof., O'zR Oliy Majlisi qonunchilik palatasi deputati
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, i.f.n., professor, MIM akademiyasi rektori
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, i.f.d., prof., TDIU Ilmiy ishlar va innovatsiyalar bo'yicha prorektori
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, i.f.d., prof., Navoiy davlat pedagogika instituti rektori
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, p.f.f.d., (PhD), Buxoro muhandislik-texnologiya instituti rektori
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, i.f.d., prof., TDIU Hududiy ta'lim muassasalari va markazlar bo'yicha prorektor v.b.
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, i.f.d., TDIUprofessori
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, i.f.n., TDIU professori
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, t.f.d., Rossiya xalqlar do'stligi universiteti professori
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, i.f.d., prof., Xalqaro "Nordik" universiteti rektori
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, i.f.d., TSUE professori
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixo'ja o'g'li, i.f.f.d., TDIU dotsenti
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farxod, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi IJQKD boshlig'i
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, i.f.d., TDIU professori
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, SamDu IS instituti professori
Cham Tat Huei, (PhD) USCI universiteti professori, Malayziya
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, i.f.f.d.,(PhD) "El-yurt umidi" jamg'armasi ijrochi direktori o'rinbosari
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, t.f.f.d.,(PhD) TAQU katta o'qituvchisi
Djudi Smetana, p.f.n., Pitsburg davlat universiteti dosenti, Pittsburgh, Kansas, AQSH
Krissi Lyuis, p.f.n., Pitsburg davlat universiteti dosenti, Pittsburgh, Kansas, AQSH
Ali Konak (Али Кўнак), i.f.d., prof., Karabuk universiteti dosenti, Turkiya
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, i.f.n., "LUKOIL-Energoservis" Kompaniyasi iqtisodchisi, Moskva.
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, i.f.f.d., (PhD) TDIU dotsenti
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, PhD, Turkiya Anqara universiteti doktoranti
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Maxamatjon o'g'li, TDIU mustaqil tadqiqotchisi

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

Salimov Oqil Umrzokovich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan

Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjaevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan

Rae Kwon Chung, honorary professor of TSUE, Nobel laureate, South Korea,

Osman Mesten, member of the Turkish Parliament, head of the Turkey-Uzbekistan Friendship Society

Sharipov Kongratbay Avezimbetovich, DSc, Prof., Minister of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Buzrukkhanov Sarvarkhan Munavvarkhanovich, DSc, Deputy Minister of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, DSc, Prof., Deputy of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich CSc, Prof., Rector of Academy of Labor and Social Relations

Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, DSc, Prof., TSUE Vice-Rector for Scientific Affairs and Innovation

Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhritdinovich, DSc, Prof., Rector of the Navoi State Pedagogical Institute

Siddikova Sadokat Ghaforovna, PhD, Rector of the Bukhara Institute of Engineering and Technology

Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, DSc, Prof., acting Vice-rector for regional educational institutions and centers of TSUE

Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, DSc, Prof., of TSUE

Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, CSc, Prof., of TSUE

Slizovsky Dimitriy Yegorovich, DSc, Prof., of the People's Friendship University of Russia

Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, DSc, Prof., Rector of International "Nordic" University

Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, DSc, Prof., of TSUE

Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixo'ja ugli, DSc, Prof., of TSUE

Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Head of the DGPO of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Ochilov Farkhod, Head of the DCECGPO of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Eshtayev Alisher Abduganievich, DSc, Prof., of TSUE

Shoira Azimovna Musaeva, professor of SamDu IS Institute

Cham Tat Huei, PhD, professor at USCI University, Malaysia

Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, PhD, deputy of executive director of the "El-yurt umidi" fund

Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, PhD, Senior Lecturer at Tashkent University of Architecture and Construction

Judy Smetana CSc, Associate Professor, Pittsburgh State University, Pittsburgh, Kansas, USA

Chrissy Lewis CSc, Associate Professor, Pittsburgh State University, Pittsburgh, Kansas, USA

Ali Konak DSc, Prof., Associate Professor of Karabuk University, Turkey

Glazova Marina Viktorovna, CSc, economist at LUKOIL-Energoservis Company, Moscow.

Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, associate professor of TSUE

Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, PhD, doctoral student at Ankara University, Turkey

Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon ugli, independent researcher of TSUE

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, t.f.d., profesor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, f.f.d., TDIU professori
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, i.f.d., TDIU professori
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, i. f. n., TDAU dotsenti
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, f.f.n., Farg'ona davlat universiteti dotsenti
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, i.f.d, TDIU dotsenti
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, i.f.f.d., TDIU dotsenti
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, p.f.f.d., (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, i.f.f.d. (PhD), Alfraganus universiteti dotsenti
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, i.f.f.d, TDIU dotsenti
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, i.f.d., TMI dotsenti
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, TDIU mustaqil tadqiqotchisi

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

Avtosanoat korxonalarini marketing strategiyasini takomillashtirish yo'llari	16
Qo'ng'iroqboy Avezimbetovich Sharipov, Zayniddinova Umida Djalolovna	
Mamlakat raqamli iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishda maxsus iqtisodiy zonalarda omilidan foydalanish istiqbollari	26
Izbosarov Boburjon Baxriddinovich, Abdurasulov Ravshanbek Xotam o'g'li	
Mahalla institutini ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlantirishning institutsional tahlili	32
Bahriddinov Viqorjon Akbar o'g'li	
Mamlakatimizda pillachilik biznesini rivojlantirish orqali mahsulot ishlab chiqarish va uni qayta ishlash holatining tahlili	37
Turgunov Odilbek Maripovich	
Etnografik turizmni tashkil etishning xorij tajribasi	41
I. Axmedov	
Xizmatlar sohasining milliy iqtisodiyotdagi rolini tahlil qilishning zamonaviy yondashuvlari.....	46
Xusanov Murodjon Sunnatullayevich	
Iqtisodiy o'sish tushunchasi va uning rivojlanish tarixi.....	54
Maksudov Avazbek Ulug'bek o'g'li	
Ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy jarayonlarni takomillashtirish asosida inson kapitalini rivojlantirish	59
Ubaydullaev G'ayrat Zuvaytovich	
O'zbekistonda aholi bandligini ta'minlashda oilaviy tadbirkorlikning o'rni.....	65
Baymanova Mavlyuda Djurayevna	
The Effect of Students' Financial Status on Academic Performance in Uzbekistan	70
Alimov Damirjon Odilovich	
Qoraqalpog'iston Respublikasida xizmat ko'rsatish sohasida tadbirkorlik faoliyatining o'rni.....	76
Jusupova Anjim Tansiqbaevna	
Insurance Mechanisms in Foreign Trade: Mitigating Risk and Facilitating Global Commerce	82
Sohibjamol Abirkulova	
Nodavlat umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktabning faoliyati samaradorligini aniqlashdaining innovatsion usullardan foydalanish	87
Ustadjalilova Xurshida Aliyevna	
Qishloq xo'jaligi korxonalarida asosiy vositalar hisobi va auditi bo'yicha xorijiy tajribalar va ulardan respublikamizda foydalanish imkoniyatlari.....	92
Xojimurodov Zuxriddin Shukurullo o'g'li	
O'zbekiston Respublikasi budjetining shakllanishida egri soliqlarni undirishning fiskal samaradorligi.....	97
Abdulxayeva Shahnova Muxammadiyevna	
Mamlakat sanoatining barqaror rivojlanishida energosamaradorlikning roli.....	104
J. J. Yaxshilikov	
Сравнительный анализ состояния сферы услуг в регионах Андижанской области.....	109
Мусабоев Рустам Алижонович	
Hududlarda aholi bandligini oshirish va kambag'allikni qisqartirishda ishlab chiqarish sanoatining o'rni (Qashqadaryo viloyati misolida.....)	114
Hamdamov Shahzod Ilhom o'g'li, Baxronov Baxriddin Najmiddinovich	
Banklarning qimmatli qog'ozlar bozorida faoliyatini takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	118
Ermatov Utkirbek Baxodirjonovich	

Развитие цифровой экономики в Узбекистане, ее плюсы и минусы	122
Раупова Муҳлисахон Ибраҳимжон кизи, Мамбетова Мадина Зоҳид кизи, Алижонова Малика Алижон кизи, Ҳақимова Нигора Бахтиёрвна	
Investment Management is an Important Factor of Economic Development.....	127
Yuldasheva G. A., Ziyayev Dilshodjon	
O'zbekistonda moliyaviy texnologiyalar sanoatining rivojlanish istiqbollari.....	130
Rustamov Jasurbek Ravshanbek o'g'li	
Davlat-xususiy sherikchilik asosidagi loyihalarni moliyalashtirish.....	136
Toyirov Yunus Alamovich	
Operatsion faoliyatni boshqarishda strategiya tushunchasiga bo'lgan yondashuvlarning shakllanishi.....	143
Dedajanov Baxtiyor Nabijanovich	
Ta'lim jarayoniga raqamli texnologiyalarni joriy etish orqali ta'lim sifati va samaradorligini ta'minlash.....	148
Xusniddinov Yorqinjon Muxiddin o'g'li	
Budjet tashkilotlarida pul mablag'lari nazorat qilishni rivojlantirish yo'llari.....	152
Alimardonov Muxammadi Ibragimovich, Djalilova Malika Shuxratovna	
QQS ma'murchiligining yevropa tajribasi.....	157
Bisenbayev Sharyar Kuanishbayevich	
O'zbekistonda soliq yukiga ta'sir etuvchi omillar tahlili	162
Nasimov Ravshanjon Azimovich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida muqobil energiya vositalaridan foydalanib ma'lumot almashinish va iqtisodiy samaradorlikni oshirish masalalari	170
Ashurov Azizbek Ergash o'g'li, Janzakov Bekzot	
Analysis of the theoretical foundations of sustainable economic development at regional level	175
Khudayorova Munira Omonboy kizi	
Soliq ma'murchiligida joriy etilgan jismoniy shaxslardan olinadigan soliqlarni undirish mexanizmini takomillashtirish yo'llari	182
Muxtorov Zokir Sayfulla o'g'li, Karimov Ilhom Anorboy o'g'li, Homidov Asrorbek Tohirjon o'g'li, Axmedova Shoxista G'ayrat qizi	
Sirdaryo viloyatining investitsiya muhiti zamonaviy rivojlanish tendensiyalari	187
Xolmurotova Diyoraxon Ibragimovna	
Transformatsiyalash jarayonida tijorat banklarining kreditlash faoliyatini rivojlantirishning nazariy asoslari.....	191
Razzoqov Bexzod Gofurovich	
Modern trends in assessing the impact of industrial development on the environment.....	196
Turg'unov Jasurbek Alimardon o'g'li	
Pul oqimlarini guruhlash mezonlari bo'yicha tasniflashni kengaytirish.....	202
Atamurodov Saidmurod Yaxyoevich	
Iqlim o'zgarishlari va uning iqtisodiy rivojlanishga ta'sirining ilmiy-nazariy tahlili	208
Ashrafjon Elov	
Soliqlarning iqtisodiy mohiyati va ahamiyati	214
Abramatov Eldor Toshmamatovich, Alimov Abduraxon Alxamiddin o'g'li, Shodmonqulov Temurbek Ulug'bek o'g'li, Nurillayev Jasurbek Davronbekovich	
Tijorat banki daromadlari - moliyaviy barqarorlikni omili sifatida.....	218
Umarov Davron Shavkatovich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida korxonalar barqarorligini boshqarishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	223
Masharipova Manzura Alimbayevna, Rahimov Mirjalol Sultonboy o'g'li	
Innovatsion yondashuvlar asosida chakana savdoni rivojlantirish yo'nalishlari.....	227
Saparova Mohira Alisher qizi, Abdullayev Ilyos Sultanovich	

Experience of foreign countries in youth labor market research 231 Asqarova Muhabbat Ibraximovna	231
Xorij mamlakatlarida ijtimoiy tibbiy sug'urta badallari qiymatlarini taqqoslash 235 Umurzakova Mo'tabarxon Nodir qizi	235
O'zbekistonda alkogol va tamaki mahsulotlari ishlab chiqarilishi hamda realizatsiya qilinishi tahlili 241 Eshmatov Sirojiddin Tog'aymurodovich	241
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarini xalqaro tasnifining vujudga kelishi ilg'or tajribalari 247 Yuldashev Iskandar Bahromovich	247
Анализ зарубежного опыта методологии оценки финансового потенциала развитых стран 253 Буранова Лола Вахобовна	253

EXPERIENCE OF FOREIGN COUNTRIES IN YOUTH LABOR MARKET RESEARCH

ORCID: 0009-0002-0121-7925

Askarova Muhabbat

“Economy of Uzbekistan” under TDIU
scientific foundations and problems of development”
senior researcher of the scientific research center

Abstract: In this article, the problems related to the development of the youth labor market and solutions and proposals aimed at preventing them, as well as the methods of using foreign experience in researching the youth labor market, are highlighted.

Key words: youth labor market, employment, unemployment, infrastructure, economic growth, labor resources, salary, youth employment.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada yoshlar mehnat bozorini rivojlantirish bilan bog'liq muammolar va ularning oldini olishga qaratilgan yechim va takliflar, shuningdek, yoshlar mehnat bozorini tadqiq etishning xorij tajribasidan foydalanish usullari yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: yoshlar mehnat bozori, bandlik, ishsizlik, infratuzilma, iqtisodiy o'ish, mehnat resurslari, maosh, yoshlar bandligi.

Аннотация: В данной статье освещены проблемы, связанные с развитием молодежного рынка труда и пути их решения и предложения, направленные на их предотвращение, а также методы использования зарубежного опыта исследования молодежного рынка труда.

Ключевые слова: туристическая инфраструктура, занятость, безработица, экотуризм, молодежный рынок труда, занятость, безработица, инфраструктура, экономический рост, трудовые ресурсы, заработная плата, занятость молодежи.

INTRODUCTION

In today's world, in many countries, understanding the youth labor market is becoming crucial for policymakers and economists to create strategies that support the transition of young people from education to the workforce, reduce youth unemployment and address issues of underemployment rate. Unfortunately, the position of labor market is disappointing in most countries of the world as shown by the generally scanty labor market indices: high rates of unemployment and NEET (not in education, employment or training), and low activity and employment rates. It is just amazing that many young population get university degree, however not many of them have or find appropriate jobs for themselves. According to the world statistics, in the world, labor force participation rate among youth between 2000 and 2023 declined gradually that in 2000, it was about 51,29%, in 2023, it this indication dropped to 40,33% respectively¹. The decline must be seen in relation with increasing levels of development, which usually comes with increasing education and hence, lower youth employment.

On April 26, 2023, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted a decree “On additional measures to support the employment of young people and provide them with permanent employment” The purpose of the decree is to expand the conditions for young people to start an independent life in our country, to fully demonstrate their talent and potential, to support their employment, to ensure that they get permanent work and a decent income².

There is an additional problem: even when youngsters obtain an occupation, they often hold a precarious job position, for instance, in the informal labor market or a temporary contract, frequently in low-paid and poorly qualified occupations; thus, young workers are usually the first ones to lose their job when an economic crisis occurs. The “working poor” phenomenon, relatively extended among young generations, clearly contrasts with the “decent job” aim, settled by international organizations, such as ILO.

1 World statista.com

2 <https://lex.uz/docs/-6442039>

LITERATURE REVIEW

In the whole world, scientists are conducting research on youth unemployment and problems in the formation of the youth labor market.

From foreign researchers, according to the notions of the Richard Freeman in the National Bureau of Economic Research (NBER), there are two basic causes of high youth joblessness: a) According to the demand view, the principal reason for high and increased joblessness is the lack of adequate demand for young workers due to such factors as slow economic growth, cyclical weaknesses in the economy, changes in the mix of jobs which alter the level of demand and minimum wages which reduce employment due to high costs of labor; b) According to the supply view, the principal reason for high and increased youth joblessness is a lack of skills, incentives and/or aspirations on the part of the young³. Berna Kahraman's study named: "Youth employment and unemployment in developing countries: Macro challenges with micro perspectives" is focused on concerns the impact of individual supply factors on youth outcomes in Turkey. The roles of human capital factors such as education and of family factors such as parent and sibling characteristics related to social capital were tested using micro data from the Turkish Household Labor Force Survey and hierarchical modeling. The study also tested the impact of the structural characteristics of regions⁴. In the research done by Zixin Yang, the effects of transportation development on differences in labor market outcomes by ethnicity have been estimated.

According to the Uzbek scientists, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan Q.K. Abdurahmanov said that "human resources are the subject of economic relations due to the demand for and supply of human capital, as well as other economic indicators" explained the different aspects.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The article uses research methods of scientific abstraction, empirical, descriptive statistics, grouping, comparison, and dynamic analysis.

DISCUSSIONS AND RESULTS

We know that in developed countries, the youth labor market has distinct characteristics as well as faces many opportunities. For instance, in developed countries, significant proportions of youth pursue high education, leading to a well-educated workforce, however, this can result in delayed entry into the labor market. Furthermore, technology and innovation that developed countries often have advanced technological infrastructures, providing youth with opportunities in high-tech industries and innovation driven sectors.

If we look at the the youth labor market in Japan, there is not huge difference between the youth unemployment rate for a long time. The youth unemployment rate in Japan decreased by 0.2 percentage points (-4.52 percent) in 2023 in comparison to the previous year. Nevertheless, the last two years recorded a significant higher youth unemployment rate than the preceding years⁵. As in other countries, youth employment in Japan is directly affected by the economy, but one reason the impact tends to be particularly significant in Japan is the system of "simultaneous mass recruiting of new graduates. In 2003, the government formulated the Plan to Encourage Youth's Independence and Challenges, acknowledging for the first time that young people's lack of job security was not a personal responsibility but a structural problem. Subsequently, career education was expanded, and based on a German model, a Japanese "dual system" that integrates vocational training at schools with corporate internships was developed, along with live-in vocational training facilities that promote young people's independence (not currently existent).

In 2006, Regional Youth Support Stations (RYSS) were opened to provide assistance to NEETs, and Hello Work for the youth and Hello Work for new graduates were also established as specialist branches of Hello Work, the public employment security offices located in all prefectures. However, these were temporary policies and there was always concern that they would be terminated. Thus, a permanent policy to support youth (the Youth Employment Promotion Act) was formulated in 2015. In addition to providing for the establishment of youth support organizations such as RYSS, the following three measures were added based on the Youth Employment Promotion Act.⁶

According to the world statistics, outh unemployment rate in the United States, in 2023, nearly unchanged at around 7.98 percent. Without a doubt, youngs employment rate is very crucial for the United States. In order

3 Why is there a youth labor market problem?, national bureau of economic research 1050 Massachusetts Avenue Cambridge MA 02138 June 1979

4 Berna Kahraman, "Youth Employment And Unemployment In Developing Countries: Macro Challenges With Micro Perspectives", PhD diss, 2011.

5 <https://www.statista.com/statistics/812126/youth-unemployment-rate-in-japan>

6 Youth Employment and Employment Policies in Japan, Japan Labor Issues Volume 7 Number 41, January, 2023

to provide the youth with employment, in US, some “**The Youth Employment Strategies**”⁷ can help employers fill gaps in the workforce while providing young people with training, work experience and pay:

1. Work-Based Learning

Work-based learning can start as early as elementary school, but can extend through high school and even to community colleges and universities. Work-based learning involves a wide array of strategies that offer students experiential opportunities to explore careers; legislative interest in these programs is growing. Examples of work-based learning can be anything from career fairs and career counseling to internships and even to apprenticeships. Successful work-based learning programs provide students the opportunity to explore numerous career paths and then gain experience in their industry of choice.

2. Apprenticeship

Apprenticeships are work-based learning programs completed under the supervision of a master or senior worker that include both a paid work and an educational component. Apprenticeship programs can be desirable because they provide workers with a job upfront, allowing them to immediately begin collecting wages while receiving classroom instruction and additional training. Additionally, these programs are designed to culminate in the completion of a skilled labor certification or even a four-year degree, providing workers with valuable credentials to land well-paying jobs. According to “Jobs for the Future”, the number of new youth apprentices grew per year from 18,877 to 40,293, an increase of 113%.

3. Credentials

A credential is an acknowledgement authorized by a third party, such as a trade union, community college or industry group, that certifies the holder in a particular skill. Credentials can include a range of programs, such as certificates, industry certifications, “microcredentials,” and occupational licenses. These programs tend to be a faster and cheaper alternative to a four-year college degree.

Besides that, in America, Workforce Innovation and Opportunity act (WIOA) provides funding for program that support youth employment, including job training, education and support service.

Looking to the experience of Singapore in this problems of the youth labor market, this country use “**Skills-Future**” which provides lifelong learning and skills upgrading. This system also provides credits for citizens to take courses and attend workshops.

The youth employment rate in Uzbekistan, in 2023, decreased by 0.4 percentage points (-3.65 percent) since the previous year. The youth unemployment rate refers to the share of the economically active population aged 15 to 24 currently without work but in search of employment. The youth unemployment rate does not include economically inactive persons such as the long-term unemployed or full-time students⁸.

We know that the employment of young people in Uzbekistan and their ability to find their place in life is at the highest level in our country. The year 2021 in our country is “Supporting the youth and strengthening the health of the population year” was announced. This is definitely a clear example of attention paid to young people. In addition, the youth policy established by our government has two main directions: providing modern education and providing employment to young people.

According to official statistics, the number of unemployed people in the country was 1.3 million. In 2024, another 2.4 million people will enter the labor market.⁹ Taking this into account, it is planned to provide employment to 5 million people due to the creation of new jobs in 2024. In particular, it is possible to create 2.5 million jobs in the service sector, 2.1 million in agriculture, 250 thousand in investment projects and industry, and 140 thousand in construction.¹⁰ The service sector has the potential to provide employment to 2.5 million labor resources, especially in this sector, which will allow more young people to be employed. For example, if almost 7 million tourists visit our country in 2023, all of them will use services, and we can say that the formation of more service sector workers by young people will cause an increase in the level of employment.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, different countries adopt varying strategies to combat the problems related to the youth unemployment rate, as well as, these countries are trying to great contribution to the country’s economy with providing employment among youngsters. From my prospective, I would argue some some proposals which could be useful to address this problem in our country.

1. Expanding vocational Training programs can encourage the young people to find their right path in life, because not all youngs would like to take academic degree, in contrast, they may like to develop their personal skills;

⁷ Employment/strategies-for-youth-employment

⁸ World statista.com

⁹ Official statistical agency of Uzbekistan

¹⁰ Official statistical agency of Uzbekistan

2. Providing Career Counseling and Guidance, I think, can be useful for job seekers that they may provide knowledge about preparing good guidance, timetable, resume, interview preparation and others. If this experience would be adopted, our young who can face problems in their career, might reach their goals easily and fast.

Reference

1. Abdurahmonov Q.X. Labor economics theory and practice. Textbook Tashkent – 2019.
2. Berna Kahraman, "Youth Employment And Unemployment In Developing Countries: Macro Challenges With Micro Perspectives", PhD diss, 2011.
3. Kholmominov Sh.R. Formation and development of the rural labor market and their modeling (Monograph). –T.: "Science and technology", 2014.; Khomitov K.Z. Problems of effective development of the rural labor market of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Dissertation for the degree of Doctor of Economics. –T.: Institute of Economics of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2012.
4. Kholmammedov M.M. Regulation and improvement of youth employment in the labor market (on the example of Samarkand region). Dissertation for the degree of Candidate of Economic Sciences. – Samarkand, 2011.
5. Nasimov D.A. Improving the system of employment of graduates of higher education institutions (on the example of Samarkand region). Dissertation for the degree of Candidate of Economic Sciences. – Samarkand, 2011.
6. Speech by President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the 72nd session of the United Nations General Assembly on 19 September. <http://uza.uz/uz/posts/zbekiston-president>.
7. Why is there a youth labor market problem?, national bureau of economic research 1050 Massachusetts Avenue Cambridge MA 02138 June 1979.
8. Xudayberdiev Z.Ya. Entrepreneurship and employment technology. Study guide. "SCIENCE" 2016.
9. Youth Employment and Employment Policies in Japan, Japan Labor Issues Volume 7 Number 41, January, 2023.
10. Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Annual demographic collection of Uzbekistan" T.: –2022. 96 pages.
11. <http://mehnat.uz>.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Xondamir Ismoilov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2024. № 7

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin.

Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: [@iqtisodiyot_77](https://t.me/@iqtisodiyot_77)

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, [@iqtisodiyot_77](https://t.me/@iqtisodiyot_77) telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

